

DISASTER PREPAREDNESS AND PERCEPTIONS OF GENDER ROLES IN DISASTER MANAGEMENT

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Keywords

Disaster Preparedness,

Disaster Management,

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to examine individuals' levels of disaster preparedness and their perceptions of gender roles in disaster management prior to the 6 February 2023 earthquakes in Hatay Province. This cross-sectional study was conducted with 1,422 participants. Data were collected using the Disaster Preparedness Scale (DPS) and the Perception Scale of Gender Roles in Disaster Management (PSGRDM). Descriptive statistics and comparative analyses were performed to evaluate relationships between variables. Of the participants, 66.8% were women and 85.7% were aged between 18 and 29 years. The mean DPS score was 33.50 ± 8.85 , and the mean PSGRDM score was 71.73 ± 13.05 . Married participants had significantly higher DPS scores than unmarried participants ($p = 0.015$). Individuals who had received disaster-related training, were familiar with the Turkish Disaster Response Plan (TAMP: Türkiye Afet Müdahale Planı), or had prior disaster experience showed significantly higher preparedness levels ($p < 0.05$). Women reported higher PSGRDM scores compared to men, indicating greater awareness of gender roles in disaster management. Additionally, participants with a bachelor's degree or higher had significantly higher PSGRDM scores than those with lower educational levels ($p < 0.001$). Improving disaster preparedness requires expanding education and training programs as well as increasing public awareness. Promoting gender equality in disaster management is also crucial for reducing the adverse impacts of disasters and ensuring more inclusive and effective response strategies.

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that societies have been exposed to numerous disasters of various types and magnitudes throughout history¹. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines a disaster as “a sudden ecological event of such magnitude that it requires external assistance”². Disasters are accepted as a natural part of human life and affect all societies worldwide, either directly or indirectly. However, despite current knowledge and technological capabilities, the timing and impacts of disasters remain largely unpredictable³. Therefore, preventive measures and preparations taken before a disaster play a critical role in minimizing potential losses during and after the event⁴. Although large-scale disasters worldwide have made countries and institutions more aware of the need for preparedness, recent disasters have shown that this preparedness remains insufficient in many cases³.

Community-level disaster preparedness refers to the personal protective behaviors that individuals develop to safeguard their lives and property in the face of unexpected and unforeseeable situations⁵. The state of being prepared for disasters and all measures taken in this context are defined in the literature as “disaster preparedness”⁶. The state of being prepared for disasters is closely related to the concepts of risk, hazard, and vulnerability⁷. One of the key factors determining vulnerability to disasters is gender roles. This indicates that vulnerability is shaped not only by physical conditions but also by the socially constructed roles of individuals⁸. Inequalities stemming from gender roles cause women and men to be affected by disasters in different ways and increase vulnerability to disasters. Therefore, it is emphasized that policies that take gender dynamics into account in disaster risk reduction and response processes will yield more effective and inclusive results⁹. Gender refers to the socially constructed roles, patterns, opportunities, and relationships for women and men¹⁰, and requires the active participation of both genders at all stages of disaster management to build disaster-resilient societies¹¹.

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Due to its geological structure and climatic characteristics, Turkey is located in a region where various types of disasters, particularly earthquakes, occur frequently. Turkey ranks third in the world in terms of earthquake-related fatalities and eighth in terms of the number of people affected¹². Located in the southernmost part of Turkey, Hatay Province is situated on the eastern coast of the Mediterranean Sea and carries a high risk of earthquakes due to its position along active fault lines¹³. The primary reason for conducting this study in Hatay Province is the region's seismic risk, as well as the importance of determining the public's level of preparedness for disasters. Accordingly, this study aims to reveal the disaster preparedness levels of individuals living in Hatay Province and their perceptions regarding gender roles in disaster management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Type of Study

This study was designed as a descriptive and cross-sectional study.

Population and Sample

The population of the study consists of individuals residing in Hatay Province. The population size was determined to be 1,686,043 people according to 2022 data from the Turkish Statistical Institute¹⁴. The sample size was calculated using the formula $n = (Nt^2pq)/(d^2(N-1)+t^2pq)$ —a formula commonly used for known populations—to yield a minimum of 385 participants, assuming a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level.

Data Collection Process

Data were collected via an online survey between November 15, 2022, and January 15, 2023. The survey form was designed to include an informational text explaining the purpose and methodology of the study to participants. Individuals who voluntarily agreed to participate in the study were reached using snowball sampling, with the goal of exceeding the specified minimum sample size. During this process, data was collected from a total of 1,422 participants and used in the analyses.

Data Collection Tools

Research data were collected via an online survey consisting of three sections: the Personal Information Form, the Disaster Preparedness Scale, and the Perceived Gender Roles in Disaster Management Scale.

Disaster Preparedness Scale (DPS)

This scale was developed by Şentuna and Çakı (2020) to measure household disaster preparedness. Consisting of a total of 13 items, the scale is structured as a 4-point Likert scale. Scores on the scale range from 13 to 52, with higher scores indicating a higher level of disaster preparedness. In the study where the scale was developed, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient reflecting internal consistency was reported as 0.82⁷. In this study, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the scale was calculated as 0.89.

Perception Scale of Gender Role in Disaster Management (PSGRDM)

This scale was developed by Önal, Soysal, and Paksoy Erbaydar (2022) and aims to measure perceptions of gender roles in disaster management. The scale is unidimensional, consists of a total of 19 items, and is structured as a 5-point Likert scale. Two of the items are positive, while 17 are negative statements. The total score range for the scale is 19 to 95, with 19–34 indicating a completely negative perception, 35–49 a negative perception, 50–64 a neutral perception, 65–79 a positive perception, and 80–95 a completely positive perception. In the original study of the scale, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was determined to be 0.90¹⁵. In this study, the scale's internal consistency was calculated as 0.90 using the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, indicating that the scale is highly reliable.

Data Analysis

The IBM SPSS Statistics 26.0 (IBM SPSS for Windows, Version 26) software package was used to analyze the research data. To assess the normality of the data distribution, the Z-scores for skewness and kurtosis were examined. The fact that the obtained values fell within the range of -1 to +1 indicated that the data were normally distributed¹⁶. Accordingly, the independent samples t-test was applied for comparisons between two groups, while one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for comparisons involving more than two groups. In multiple comparisons, the LSD test was used depending on the homogeneity of variance of the data. Simple linear regression analysis was used to examine the relationship between Perceived Gender Roles in Disaster Management (independent variable) and Disaster Preparedness (dependent variable). Descriptive statistics, including frequency (n), percentage (%), mean (\bar{x}), and standard deviation (SD), were reported. All statistical analyses were evaluated based on a 95% confidence level and a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Aspects of the Study

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Social and Human Sciences Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee (Date: November 2, 2022; Issue No: 11; Decision No: 18; Page: 3/5). In addition, a work permit was obtained from the Hatay Governor's Office, and permissions to use the relevant scales

were obtained from their authors. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, and the research process adhered to the ethics of scientific research and publication. In the online survey form, participants were provided with the necessary information regarding the purpose of the study, data confidentiality, and participation based on the principle of voluntariness.

RESULTS

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the participants

Variables (n=1422)	n	%
Gender		
Female	950	66.8
Male	472	33.2
Age Group		
18- 29	1214	85.7
30- 39	117	8.2
40- 49	58	4.1
≥ 50	29	2.0
Marital status		
Single	1193	83.9
Married	229	16.1
Type of settlement		
Village	276	19.4
Town	518	36.4
County seat	628	44.2
Education level		
Secondary education	84	5.9
High school	204	14.3
Bachelor's degree or higher	1134	79.7
Income level		
Low	678	47.7
Medium	611	43.0
High	133	9.4
Has a close family member experienced a disaster?		
Yes	801	56.3
No	621	43.7
Have you personally experienced a disaster?		
Yes	703	49.4
No	719	50.6
Are you familiar with TAMP?		
Yes	509	35.8
No	913	64.2
Do you know the emergency assembly point?		
Yes	749	52.7
No	673	47.3
Have you received training on disasters?		
Yes	731	51.4
No	691	48.6

TAMP (Turkey Disaster Response Plan)

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the participants. Of the total sample, 66.8% (n = 950) were female. The majority of participants (85.7%, n = 1214) were aged between 18 and 29 years, and 83.9% (n = 1193) were single. Additionally, 44.2% of the participants resided in a city center, and 79.7% held a bachelor's degree or higher.

Regarding socioeconomic status, 47.7% of the participants that they were familiar with the Turkish Disaster Response reported having a low income. More than half (56.3%) had a Plan (TAMP). Furthermore, 52.7% reported knowing their first-degree relative who had experienced a disaster, while designated emergency assembly point, and 51.4% stated that 49.4% reported having personally experienced a disaster. In they had received disaster-related training (Table 1). terms of disaster awareness, 35.8% of participants indicated

Table 2. Scores obtained on the DSP and PSGRDM scales according to participants' demographic characteristics

Variables (n=1422)	DSP (X±SS)	t/F/p	PSGRDM (X±SS)	t/F/p
Gender				
Female	33.24±8.64	t=-1.547	73.52±12.35	t= 7.509
Male	34.01±9.24	p=0.122	68.11±13.66	p=0.000
Age Group				
18- 29	33.31±8.90	F=2.120	71.75±13.10	F=0.353
30- 39	34.17±7.92	p=0.096	72.30±12.26	p=0.787
40- 49	36.13±9.04		70.17±14.33	
≥ 50	33.41±9.34		71.62±11.77	
Marital status				
Single	33.25±8.92	t=-2.446	71.74±13.17	t= 0.128
Married	34.81±8.36	p=0.015	71.62±12.43	p= 0.898
Type of settlement				
Village	32.87±9.06	F=0.951	70.74±13.54	F=1.332
Town	33.53±8.78	p=0.387	71.60±13.37	p=0.264
County seat	33.75±8.80		72.26±12.54	
Education level				
Secondary education	34.26±9.18	F=0.341	67.69±15.54	F=9.308
High school	33.55±8.02	p=0.711	69.34±12.53	p=0.000
Bachelor's degree or higher	33.43±8.97		72.45±12.84	3>1,2
Has a close family member experienced a disaster?				
Yes	34.15±9.17	t=3.189	72.22±12.93	t= 1.637
No	32.66±8.34	p=0.001	71.08±13.19	p= 0.102
Have you personally experienced a disaster?				
Yes	34.08±9.06	t=2.470	71.95±13.06	t= 0.646
No	32.93±8.60	p=0.014	71.50±13.05	p=0.518
Are you familiar with TAMP?				
Yes	36.96±8.88	t=11.504	71.56±13.73	t= -0.346
No	31.57±8.16	p=0.000	71.81±12.66	p= 0.729
Do you know the emergency assembly point?				
Yes	36.22±8.66	t=12.939	72.05±12.98	t= 0.993
No	30.47±8.04	p=0.000	71.36±13.12	p= 0.321
Have you received training on disasters?				
Yes	35.54±9.03	t=9.240	71.90±13.49	t= 0.532
No	31.34±8.11	p=0.000	71.54±12.57	p= 0.595
Scale Total Scores	33.50±8.85 (13-52)		71.73±13.05 (19-95)	

t-test, ANOVA, LSD, DSP: Disaster Preparedness Scale (possible scores: 13–52), PSGRDM: Perceived Gender Roles in Disaster Management Scale (possible scores: 19–95), SS: Standard deviation

A comparison of Disaster Preparedness Scale (DPS) and Perception of Gender Roles in Disaster Management (PSGRDM) scores across demographic variables is presented in Table 2. No statistically significant difference was found in DPS scores by gender ($p > 0.05$). However, PSGRDM scores differed significantly by gender ($t = 7.509$; $p < 0.001$), with women (73.52 ± 12.35) scoring higher than men (68.11 ± 13.66). No significant differences were observed in DPS or PSGRDM scores across age groups ($p > 0.05$). A statistically significant difference in DPS scores was identified based on marital status ($t = -2.446$; $p = 0.015$), with married participants (34.81 ± 8.36) demonstrating higher preparedness levels than single participants (33.25 ± 8.92). In contrast, PSGRDM scores did not vary significantly by marital status ($p > 0.05$). No significant differences were found in DPS or PSGRDM scores according to type of settlement ($p > 0.05$). While DPS scores did not differ significantly by education level ($p > 0.05$), PSGRDM scores showed a significant difference ($F = 9.308$; $p < 0.001$). Post-hoc analysis (LSD) indicated that participants with a bachelor's degree or higher (72.45 ± 12.84) had significantly higher PSGRDM scores than those with lower levels of education.

Participants who had a first-degree relative with disaster experience had significantly higher DPS scores (34.15 ± 9.17) compared to those who did not (32.66 ± 8.34) ($t = 3.189$; $p = 0.001$). Similarly, individuals who had personally experienced a disaster demonstrated higher preparedness levels (34.08 ± 9.06) than those without such experience (32.93 ± 8.60) ($t = 2.470$; $p = 0.014$). However, PSGRDM scores did not differ significantly in either case ($p > 0.05$). Participants who were familiar with TAMP had significantly higher DPS scores (36.96 ± 8.88) than those who were not (31.57 ± 8.16) ($t = 11.504$; $p < 0.001$). Likewise, those who knew their emergency assembly point (36.22 ± 8.66) had higher preparedness levels than those who did not (30.47 ± 8.04) ($t = 12.939$; $p < 0.001$). Participants who had received disaster-related training also showed significantly higher DPS scores (35.54 ± 9.03) compared to those who had not (31.34 ± 8.11) ($t = 9.240$; $p < 0.001$). No statistically significant differences were found in PSGRDM scores for these variables ($p > 0.05$). Overall, the mean DPS score was 33.50 ± 8.85 , and the mean PSGRDM score was 71.73 ± 13.05 (Table 2).

Table 3. Results of the Regression Analysis Examining the Relationship Between PSGRDM and DPS

Variables	B	Std. error	β	t	p
Constant	47.110	1.260		37.400	.000
PSGRDM	-.190	.017	-.280	-10.979	.000
Dependent variable: DSP					
R=0.280	R ² =0.078	F= 120.533	P=0.000	Durbin Watson=1.930	

DSP: Disaster Preparedness Scale, PSGRDM: Perceived Gender Roles in Disaster Management Scale

Table 3 presents the results of the regression analysis examining the relationship between PSGRDM and DPS. The model was found to be statistically significant ($F = 120.533$; $p < 0.001$). PSGRDM explained 7.8% of the variance in DPS ($R^2 = 0.078$), indicating a limited but significant explanatory power. The regression analysis revealed that PSGRDM had a negative and statistically significant effect on DPS ($\beta = -0.280$; $t = -10.979$; $p < 0.001$). This finding suggests that perceptions of gender roles in disaster management are a significant, albeit weak, predictor of disaster preparedness levels.

DISCUSSION

Disasters are events that can occur at any time and in any place without warning, capable of causing serious and devastating

effects on individuals, families, and communities. Varying in terms of their impact and scope, disasters pose a multidimensional threat to people's lives¹⁷. An examination of disaster distribution in Turkey reveals that earthquake-related risks are quite high and that the country is situated in an earthquake-prone region. This situation makes determining individual preparedness levels critical not only for the safety of individuals but also for the overall security of society. Determining the level of disaster preparedness contributes significantly to identifying challenges in disaster management, preventing loss of life and illness, and ultimately achieving sustainable development goals^{18,19,20}. In this study, the mean total score on the Disaster Preparedness Scale (DPS) for participants was determined to be 33.50 ± 8.85 . Considering the minimum and maximum score range on the scale (13–52),

this result indicates that participants' level of disaster preparedness is moderate. Similarly, studies conducted in Turkey by Tercan (2022) and Demirci (2023) also reported that individuals' disaster preparedness levels were moderate^{21,22}. However, there are also studies in the literature indicating that individuals' preparedness levels are high^{23,24}. On the other hand, a study by Demirci (2021) revealed that individuals' basic disaster knowledge and awareness levels are low²⁵. The international literature also points to similar findings. Some studies conducted in various countries indicate that individuals' levels of preparedness for disasters are insufficient^{19,26,27,28,29}. In this study, the fact that disaster preparedness levels among individuals living in Hatay Province—an area with active fault lines and a high risk of earthquakes—are only moderate indicates that disaster awareness has not yet reached an adequate level. Consequently, disaster awareness and individual preparedness are among the critical issues that must be addressed with the utmost seriousness at both the national and global levels.

This study found that married individuals have higher levels of disaster preparedness than single individuals. This finding is consistent with the study by Ağahan and Demirbilek (2023)²³. The fact that married individuals bear the responsibility of protecting their family members, particularly their children, may have led them to be more sensitive to disasters and, consequently, to score higher. However, Tercan's (2022) research yielded the opposite result; it was noted that single individuals had higher levels of disaster preparedness²². This suggests that the effect of an individual's marital status on disaster preparedness may vary depending on socio-cultural and individual factors.

According to the study findings, 49.4% of the participants had previously experienced a disaster, and these individuals' levels of disaster preparedness were found to be significantly higher than those of participants who had not experienced a disaster. This result is consistent with similar studies in the literature. It has also been noted by Choi et al. (2022) and Stewart et al. (2017) that individuals with disaster experience have higher perceptions of disaster preparedness^{20,30}. It can be argued that disaster experience increases individuals' risk perception, thereby triggering behaviors such as taking precautions or seeking information, and thus positively influencing their preparedness levels. Additionally, this study found that participants who were familiar with the TAMP, knew the

emergency assembly point, and had received disaster-related training exhibited significantly higher levels of disaster preparedness. This finding is consistent with previous research^{21,30}. Education not only enhances knowledge levels but also contributes to individuals gaining awareness of how they should act during and after a disaster.

In this study, the participants' total score on the Perception Scale of Gender Role in Disaster Management (PSGRDM) was found to be 71.73 ± 13.05 . Based on this result, it can be concluded that the participants' perception of gender roles in disaster management is positive. This suggests that while there is a certain level of awareness regarding gender roles in disaster management, this awareness may not be sufficiently developed in all individuals.

This study found that women exhibit more gender-equitable attitudes toward disaster management than men. The literature indicates that the natural traits women develop while overcoming challenges stemming from gender-based differences—particularly their organizational and coordination skills—have been strengthened. Historically, it is known that women have taken on active roles in critical tasks during crises such as wars and disasters, including nursing, distributing volunteer aid, performing cleaning duties, and preparing temporary shelters. This historical and social experience indicates that women's potential roles in the disaster management process need to be reevaluated. It is crucial to effectively leverage women's supportive roles throughout the entire process, from pre-disaster preparedness activities to response and rescue operations during the disaster^{18,31}. In this context, eliminating perceptions of gender inequality in disaster management will ensure the process becomes more equitable and inclusive. One of the most effective ways for women to take on more active roles in disaster management is through education. Indeed, when supported by education, the quality of the services women provide to the public during the disaster management process improves; thus, they can become valuable resources and active participants in organization and coordination¹⁸. This study also found that participants with higher education levels exhibited more gender-equitable attitudes toward disaster management. This finding aligns with previous research supporting the positive relationship between educational level and disaster awareness^{21,25}.

The findings of the study indicate a negative and statistically significant relationship between positive (equal) perceptions of gender roles in disaster management and the level of disaster preparedness. Another study also found a weak but significant negative relationship between gender roles in disaster management and perceptions of disaster risk. As participants' perceptions of gender roles in disaster management increased, their perceptions of disaster risk decreased at a weak but statistically significant level; conversely, as perceptions of gender roles in disaster management decreased, perceptions of disaster risk increased at a weak but statistically significant level³². These findings point to a situation contrary to the expectation frequently emphasized in the literature that an egalitarian gender perspective would increase risk awareness and protective behaviors^{33,34}. It is believed that this finding from our study may stem from the discrepancy between perception and behavior. Indeed, the fact that individuals hold egalitarian attitudes does not necessarily mean that these attitudes will always translate into action. Disaster preparedness is influenced not only by individual perceptions and attitudes but also by numerous variables such as educational level, socioeconomic status, prior disaster experience, and risk perception^{35,36}. In this context, the low level of explanatory power ($R^2=0.078$) obtained in the study supports the multidimensional nature of disaster preparedness and indicates that some variables not included in the model also play a significant role. Furthermore, the practical manifestations of gender roles within the cultural context should not be overlooked, as they may directly influence disaster preparedness behaviors. In this regard, it can be assessed that more traditional role distributions may, in some cases, function to enhance preparedness behaviors; conversely, an egalitarian mindset may not produce the same effect at the behavioral level. However, the generalizability of this interpretation is limited, and the findings must be supported by different samples and variables.

Women's participation in decision-making processes and assumption of leadership roles in disaster planning, response, and reconstruction are of great importance for lifting women out of the disadvantaged position they face during disasters. Reducing the vulnerabilities women face due to gender inequality in society will not only minimize disaster risks but also enable the more effective use of women's knowledge and skills in disaster management. This will also significantly contribute to enhancing overall resilience to disasters across

society^{9,37,38}. The incorporation of a gender perspective into societal understanding and response processes regarding disasters is considered one of the key advancements in this field¹¹. Therefore, prioritizing gender equality in disaster management policies will enhance the effectiveness of crisis responses, leading to more equitable and sustainable outcomes. However, until recently, gender relations and the dimensions of gender equality in disasters have been largely overlooked; discussions on disaster management incorporating this perspective have remained quite limited. Yet, identifying gender differences in the relationship between risk perception and human behavior is of critical importance for the development of more effective and efficient risk management policies.

Disasters stand out as events in which gender inequality is starkly revealed; in this context, it is essential to highlight women's roles and contributions in disaster response processes^{39,40}. Gender-based norms can directly affect women's capacity to respond to natural disasters; therefore, a strong gender perspective in disaster management is essential for effective disaster preparedness. In Turkey as well, it is emphasized that educational and awareness-raising activities must be increased to integrate a gender perspective into disaster-related legislation¹¹. At the international level, the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015–2030), adopted in March 2015, has adopted the integration of a gender perspective into all policies and practices and the promotion of women's leadership as one of its core principles⁹. In this context, it is of great importance to prioritize disaster preparedness efforts, particularly in high-risk areas, to ensure that communities are prepared for disasters, and to continuously emphasize the importance of gender equality in disaster management.

Limitations of the Study

This study has certain limitations. First, the fact that the study was conducted as a single-center study within the borders of Hatay Province limits the direct generalizability of the findings to other regions of Turkey. Given that Turkey has many regions with distinct geographical and socio-cultural structures, multi-center studies involving participants from different regions are needed to ensure that the results can be generalized to the entire country. Additionally, the collection of data via an online survey form, while facilitating participation by individuals with internet access and high digital literacy, may

have excluded those with limited access to technology or low digital proficiency. This situation also poses the risk that certain social or economic groups may not be adequately represented in the sample. Finally, because the study employed a cross-sectional design, it was not possible to establish cause-and-effect relationships; the analysis was limited to evaluating the current situation. Therefore, longitudinal studies are recommended to track changes over time in dynamics such as disaster preparedness and gender perceptions.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the importance of enhancing disaster preparedness levels and strengthening gender perspectives in disaster management. The fact that participants' disaster preparedness levels were moderate indicates the need to increase efforts aimed at raising disaster awareness. Improving perceptions regarding gender roles in disaster management is a critical requirement for developing more inclusive and effective disaster response strategies. Ensuring that women play a more active role in disaster management processes and achieving gender equality will enhance communities' resilience to disasters. In this regard, it is recommended to expand the scope of disaster education programs, integrate a gender perspective into disaster management policies, and strengthen awareness-raising activities. Adopting gender-sensitive, participatory, and holistic approaches is of great importance for reducing disaster risks and ensuring sustainable development.

Conflicts of Interest Statement

There are no potential conflicts of interest.

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No

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